

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process, the editors of the *International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN)* request that contributors use the following guidelines and style:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc.).
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example: 60 kg N ha: not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example: 20 kg/ha.
- When using abbreviations other than for units of measure, spell out the full name the first time of reference, with abbreviations in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were or Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example: six parts; seven tractors; four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage; Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the *IRRN* should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common — not trade — names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment
- Do not include references in *IRRN* contributions.
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Tamil Nadu Agricultural University (TNAU) releases a brown planthopper (BPH)-resistant variety

TNAU in Coimbatore, India, has released Py3, a BPH-resistant rice, through Krishi Vigyan Kendra, Pondicherry. The variety, called *Bharathithasan*, is the IRRI culture IR13427-4-2, which inherits its resistance primarily from PTB33.

Py3 is resistant to BPH and white-

backed planthopper, matures in 115-120 d, and has medium, slender, white grains. Its eating quality is good. The variety is gaining popularity among farmers particularly in BPH-endemic areas, and is suitable for the Jun-planted crop in Tamil Nadu and Pondicherry.

Py3 was selected from breeding lines introduced from IRRI and evaluated by a team of scientists led by Dr. S. Chelliah, Professor of Entomology, TNAU. □

Co 43, a salt-tolerant variety for Tamil Nadu

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TNAU17005, a semidwarf, lodging-resistant rice with fine white grains and high yield potential, was released as Co 43 for general cultivation in Tamil Nadu in 1983. It performed well at the Paddy Breeding Station, TNAU, during navarai (Jan–May) and samba (Aug–Nov). From 1975 to 1981 at TNAU, it yielded an

average 6.3 t/ha, 21.5% higher than IR20 (see table). Under saline-alkaline-waterlogged conditions at Kaveripattinam, Barur, Paiyur, and Coimbatore (pH: 8.1 to 9.8 and EC: 0.3 to 1.3 dS/m), it yielded an average of 5.3 t/ha, or 56.6% higher than IR20. Co 43 also performed well at Machilipattam, Andhra Pradesh, with soil pH 8.2 and EC 9.9 dS/m and in International Rice Testing Program nursery trials.

The grain quality is good for raw and boiled rice. Co 43 is tolerant of green leafhopper and moderately resistant to blast, brown spot, and leaf blight. It can be grown in all seasons in Tamil Nadu. □

Yield performance of Co 43 in Tamil Nadu.

Year	Site	Trials (no.)	Av yield (t/ha)	Av % increase over IR20
1975–81	Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore	19	6.3	21.5
1978–80	Research stations	16	4.8	23.7
1981–82	Adaptive research trials in Tamil Nadu	43	3.4	19.5
1978	Saline-alkaline-waterlogged conditions	6	5.3	56.6